

**ORGANIZING METHODOLOGICAL WORK IN PRE-SCHOOL
EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS ON THE BASIS OF AN
INNOVATIVE APPROACH**

Olimov Sodiq

Retraining of directors and specialists of preschool education organizations and
their qualifications PhD student at the Institute of Higher Education

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Methodical work is a necessary organizational basis for forming an
innovative direction of pedagogical activity, creating a specific innovative

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Management of methodical work in a preschool educational organization
can be effectively carried out if its tasks, content, and organizational principles
are clearly and clearly understood not only by the leader and methodologist, but
also by the educator.

In general, the tasks of methodological work in kindergarten can be
formulated as follows:

formation of an innovative direction in the activity of the pedagogical team
of the preschool educational organization, which is reflected in the systematic
study, generalization and distribution of pedagogical experience, and the
implementation of the achievements of the pedagogical science ;

increase the level of theoretical (subject) and psychological-pedagogical
training;

new educational programs , curriculum options, changes to state
educational standards ;

pedagogical technologies, forms and methods of education and training;

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organization of work on the study of new regulatory documents, guidelines and methodological materials; providing scientific and methodological support to pedagogues on a diagnostic, individual and differentiated basis;
self-education;

increase the level of general professional and pedagogical culture.

The participation of pedagogues in methodical, innovative activities ultimately helps to form a personal pedagogical system, an individual style of pedagogical activity. Methodical work in the preschool educational organization allows solving problems related to the unique personality of the educator, his professional growth, helps to determine the pedagogical values that are important for both the pedagogical team of the preschool educational organization and the pedagogical staff.

The main goal of introducing innovative approaches is to ensure personal and social development of children, prepare them for future life and increase the overall efficiency of the educational institution.

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